

TOWARDS INCLUSION: BUILDING EMPLOYABILITY AND ADVOCACY THROUGH THE SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL WEEK PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This action research aimed at empowering the employability of students with special educational needs (SEN) and raising community awareness about their capabilities and potential through the implementation of the Special Educational Week Program. This study was conducted at SMK Khir Johari with the involvement of various parties, including government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), the local community, and the school community, to ensure an inclusive approach. The focus of this study is to build the self-confidence of students with SEN in social and vocational skills, while exposing them to real career opportunities through hands-on activities, career workshops, and collaborations with local industry employers. Additionally, the study evaluates the effectiveness of the program from the perspectives of teachers, participating agencies, and the community to measure the impact and level of awareness achieved regarding inclusive education practices. Through surveys, structured observations, and participant feedback, the findings reveal that the Special Educational Week Program successfully increased public understanding of Special Education and created more meaningful interactions between students with SEN and the local community. This program not only strengthens the collaboration between schools and external agencies but also empowers students to become independent and better prepared for the challenges of the working world. In conclusion, the Special Educational Week Program serves as a significant platform to promote an inclusive culture, strengthen community synergy, and provide equal opportunities for students to grow in social and economic aspects. Several improvement strategies are also suggested to ensure the sustainability and holistic success of this program in the future. As a teacher, I continuously strive to enhance and implement meaningful activities that can enrich the lives of my students and prepare them for the future. This reflective practice ensures that each initiative is aligned with the holistic development and long-term success of every student.

Keywords: Special educational needs, Inclusive education, Student empowerment, Communication, Employability skills.

INTRODUCTION

Special education in Malaysia continues to evolve in line with the nation's aspiration to ensure that every individual, regardless of background and ability, is given fair and equal access to education. The Special Education Philosophy (Falsafah Pendidikan Khas, FPK) emphasizes that every individual with special educational needs (SEN) must be given the opportunity to develop holistically—in terms of intellect, physicality, emotion, and social interaction—according to their own potential. Within this framework, inclusive education is not only viewed as a policy, but as a moral and professional responsibility to ensure that SEN learners experience meaningful and equitable learning.

The implementation of the Malaysia Education Blueprint (Pelan Pembangunan Pendidikan Malaysia, PPPM) 2013–2025 also highlights the importance of full participation of SEN students in mainstream education, as well as the development of vocational and social skills to enhance their employability. Therefore, employability becomes a crucial element in ensuring that SEN learners are not only receiving an education but are also prepared to participate in the community and workforce with greater confidence. However, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic drastically changed the educational landscape. During the Home-Based Teaching and Learning (PdPR) phase, various challenges emerged among teachers and students, especially those in special education. A study by Zainun (2023) reported that PdPR posed a significant dilemma for special education teachers in delivering vocational skills effectively. This clearly demonstrates that direct involvement and real-world experience are essential to ensuring meaningful learning for SEN learners.

Driven by this necessity, the action research approach becomes increasingly relevant. Action research not only provides teachers with the space to identify issues and improve practices but also offers an opportunity to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions through reflective processes. McNiff (2017) emphasized that action research enables teachers to become agents of change by planning actions, observing their outcomes, and reflecting for further improvement. This approach formed the foundation for the implementation of the Special Educational Week Program (SEWP) at SMK Khir Johari. SEWP is conducted annually and has undergone two major cycles (2023 and 2024). The first year served as a trial phase, facing challenges such as persuading external agencies to participate and organizing structured, meaningful activities. Only six external agencies participated at that time, and most activities were geared towards fulfilling the school's annual KPIs. However, in the second year, improvements were made with the involvement of 11 agencies, engagement with the local community, and integration of activities such as entrepreneurship, art exhibitions, mock interviews, and physical activities based on students' interests.

From a global perspective, similar approaches are not new. In the United States, Inclusive Schools Week focuses on raising awareness, strengthening inclusivity, and empowering school communities to embrace diversity as a strength (Inclusive Schools Network, 2024). Likewise, Neurodiversity Celebration Week, founded by Siena Castellon, promotes understanding of the unique qualities of neurodivergent individuals and the importance of creating a supportive environment (Wikipedia, 2024). Both of these initiatives demonstrate that special education week programs can act as catalysts for changes in societal attitudes, knowledge, and actions toward learners with special needs.

In this context, SEWP serves not only as a platform for SEN students to showcase their talents, but also as an opportunity for the community and industry to witness their true potential. The active involvement of industries such as PROTON, GIATMARA, and the Department of Social Welfare reflects the external community's readiness to become part of this inclusive effort. This comprehensive initiative effectively bridges the gap between education and the world of work through the Work-Based Learning (WBL) approach, as suggested by Mastam and Zaharudin (2024). Therefore, this study aims to reflectively evaluate the implementation of the Special Educational Week Program at SMK Khir Johari using the action research model proposed by McNiff. The main focus is to identify the strengths, challenges, and impact of the program on the employability and self-confidence of SEN students, as well as the level of community awareness of inclusive education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Inclusive education is an educational approach that emphasizes the full participation of all students, including students with special educational needs (SEN), in mainstream learning environments. According to Malaysia's Special Education Philosophy, every individual is entitled to a comprehensive and holistic education to realize their full potential. Within the Malaysia Education Blueprint (PPPM) 2013–2025, strengthening inclusive education is one of the Ministry of Education's core agendas to ensure access, equity, and quality education for all.

Local studies have shown that the implementation of inclusive education continues to face various challenges, particularly in terms of infrastructure, teacher training, and community readiness to accept SEN students. Zainun, Razalli, and Saad (2020) emphasized the importance of evaluation models such as CIPP in determining the effectiveness of vocational skills teaching among special education students. Their study proposed the use of real-life, experience-based teaching approaches to improve the employability of moderately able SEN learners.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, Zainun (2023) explored the dilemmas faced by special education teachers in implementing Home-Based Teaching and Learning (PdPR). The study noted that technological constraints, limited face-to-face support, and challenges in delivering vocational skills virtually created significant learning gaps for SEN students. This proves that special education requires direct, hands-on and socially interactive learning to achieve lasting impact.

Furthermore, a study by Zainun et al. (2021) involving Semai Indigenous students also highlighted the importance of employability development through entrepreneurship projects. In this study, students participated in bakery product preparation and sales during the Movement Control Order (MCO). Findings showed improvements in self-confidence, social interaction, and self-worth. This demonstrates that transition education and experiential learning can have a significant positive impact on SEN learners.

At the global level, programs such as Inclusive Schools Week have inspired many schools to create inclusive environments and celebrate student diversity. These initiatives emphasize collaboration between schools, parents, and communities to evaluate the strengths of the education system and identify the best ways to support all learners, including those with special needs (Inclusive Schools Network, 2024). The program also provides schools with resources and guides to foster a sustainable support culture.

Neurodiversity Celebration Week, founded by Siena Castellon, aims to challenge stereotypes about neurodivergent students and promote the acceptance of diverse ways of thinking and learning. The initiative not only celebrates the uniqueness of SEN students but also promotes understanding and support in schools, higher education institutions, and workplaces (Wikipedia, 2024). Both programs prove the effectiveness of community-based approaches in increasing awareness and support for inclusive education.

In terms of employability and transition education, Mastam and Zaharudin (2024) proposed a conceptual framework for work readiness among SEN learners. They emphasized soft skills, early exposure to workplace settings, and structured training such as Work-Based Learning (WBL) to facilitate smoother transitions from school to employment. This aligns well with the implementation of mock interviews, entrepreneurship projects, and skill showcases conducted through the SEWP program.

Additionally, the concept of Work-Based Learning has long been proven effective in enhancing the employability of SEN students through contextualized learning. This approach allows students to experience real workplace scenarios, interact with actual employers, and develop transferable skills. In the context of SEWP, activities such as mock interviews with PROTON and collaborations with GIATMARA and PDK are examples of WBL that added significant value to the students' learning journey.

Nevertheless, systematic action research on special education week programs remains limited in Malaysia. Although some schools conduct Special Education Days or Inclusive Days, there is rarely any comprehensive documentation or impact assessment. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by thoroughly evaluating the implementation of SEWP through an action research approach, and analyzing its effects on students, school communities, and external stakeholders.

This study also adopts a reflective and collaborative approach as proposed by McNiff (2017) in his action research cycle model. This process involves the implementation of planned actions, observation, reflection, and continuous improvement. It is not only relevant in the context of special education but also empowers teachers to act as agents of educational reform through meaningful and context-driven action.

In conclusion, the literature supports the notion that inclusive education and SEN employability must be reinforced through community-based intervention programs, backed by educational policies, and guided by structured reflective research. The SEWP initiative implemented at SMK Khir Johari is a concrete effort that integrates all these elements into a strategic platform. This study is therefore expected to provide practical guidance to teachers, school leaders, and policymakers in advancing special education in a more comprehensive and sustainable manner.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed an action research approach introduced by McNiff (2017) as the primary framework for implementation and reflection. Action research enables teachers to conduct educational interventions in a systematic, reflective, and continuous manner to improve teaching practices and address real issues within their specific context. In this study, the implementation of the Special Educational Week Program (SEWP) was used as the intervention to assess its effects on the employability and self-confidence of students with special educational needs (SEN).

This study employed an action research model developed by McNiff (2017), known as the action-reflection cycle. This involved the process of observing, reflecting, action, evaluating, modifying and subsequently planning new actions (see Figure 1). The use of action-reflection cycles in this study helped the practitioner act as a researcher to develop new practices, knowledge, ideas and theories (McNiff, 2017). Each cycle provides practitioners with the opportunity to strategically plan their actions, carry them out, observe the effectiveness of implementation, and conduct reflective evaluations for improvement in subsequent cycles. This approach is highly suitable for special education teachers as it allows for real-time monitoring of student behavior changes and progress

Figure 1: McNiff's Action Research Cycle (Adapted from McNiff, 2017)

The SEWP program was implemented in two cycles, in 2023 and 2024. The first cycle (2023) served as a pioneering phase and presented multiple challenges as the implementer had to convince external agencies to participate, structure the activities effectively, and ensure smooth execution with limited resources. Key activities in this phase included the official launch of SEWP, scout camping, mock interviews, school-wide e-quiz, community visits, gross and fine motor activities (grossfinetivity), and a closing appreciation ceremony.

However, observations and reflections from the first cycle revealed that the activities conducted lacked clear focus on the actual objective of student employability. Many of the activities were more aligned with fulfilling annual Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and did not strongly emphasize assessment of student development. Therefore, improvements were implemented in the second cycle (2024), with the number of external agencies participating increasing from six to eleven. These included major industry and government stakeholders such as PROTON, GIATMARA, the Department of Social Welfare (JKM), Community-Based

Rehabilitation Centre (PDK), National Youth Skills Institute (IKBN), and other local industry representatives.

In the second cycle, the activities were more organized and targeted, featuring a two-day Entrepreneurship Fair, an Arts and Bead Crafts Exhibition, Open Karaoke, Mock Interviews, a Mini Career Fair, and sports-based activities such as Archery Combat and Fun Shoot. The direct involvement of industry representatives provided students with a clearer and more realistic understanding of the working world. The quality of interaction between students and agencies also improved significantly, which positively impacted on students' motivation and their understanding of workplace expectations.

Data collection instruments included questionnaires, observation checklists, and written and verbal feedback from teachers, students, agencies, and community members. Questionnaires were distributed to special education teachers and subject teachers who were involved in the program. Observations were conducted informally by program advisors and facilitators throughout the implementation. Feedback from agency representatives was obtained both verbally and in writing during the program's closing sessions and through their participation in field activities.

The data were analyzed both descriptively and reflectively by identifying key themes that emerged from respondent answers and observation notes. The findings were analyzed from several perspectives: student impact (self-confidence, communication, vocational skills), agency collaboration, and community awareness of the role of special education. These analyses formed the basis for evaluating the effectiveness of the intervention and for suggesting improvements to the program in the future.

In terms of ethics, this study adhered to basic principles of educational ethics. All participant information was kept confidential and not disclosed individually. Student faces in photos included in the report were blurred to protect their privacy. All participants were informed of the program's objectives, and participation was entirely voluntary.

As the implementer of this action research, my role as a teacher was essential in every aspect—from planning to reflection. I functioned not only as a facilitator and program coordinator, but also as an active observer, reflective recorder, and liaison between the school, agencies, and community. My direct presence in all activities allowed me to gain a comprehensive understanding of students' needs and to adapt teaching approaches to the real-life context of each student.

In summary, the methodology of this study was designed based on the need to evaluate the real-world impact of an intervention in the context of special education. It provided me, as a teacher, with the opportunity to act professionally, reflectively, and effectively in designing and evaluating the SEWP program as a strategic intervention for inclusive education and the empowerment of SEN student employability.

RESULTS AND FINDING

The implementation of the Special Educational Week Program (SEWP) at SMK Khir Johari was carried out in two main phases or action research cycles: Cycle 1 (2023) and Cycle 2 (2024). Both cycles provided important data for evaluating the program's impact on student employability, community awareness, and the level of participation and support from external agencies.

Cycle 1: Initial Implementation and Challenges

Cycle 1 began with various activities including the official launch of SEWP, scout camping, internal mock interviews, a school-wide e-quiz, community visits, grossfinitivity activities, and an appreciation ceremony. However, the implementation was challenging, as only six external agencies agreed to participate, and many activities were conducted hastily to fulfill the school's annual KPIs.

Reflections revealed that the activities were not sufficiently focused on the program's core objectives. For example, the mock interviews were conducted without the involvement of actual industry representatives, which prevented students from gaining authentic insight into the world of work. Similarly, the community visits offered limited opportunities for meaningful two-way interaction. Initial data collected from teachers and agency feedback indicated that only 68% of respondents felt the program had a direct impact on student employability.

Cycle 2: Strategic Improvements and Increased Impact

The second cycle demonstrated significant improvements in terms of program structure, the number of participating agencies (11 agencies), and more meaningful activity content. Key activities included a two-day Entrepreneurship Fair, an Arts and Bead Craft Exhibition, casual Karaoke sessions, industry-led Mock Interviews (with representatives from PROTON, GIATMARA, IKBN), a Mini Career Fair, Archery Combat, and Fun Shoot activities.

The implementation process was evaluated from several angles, such as student interactions with employers and industry facilitators, the demonstration of real skills through product sales and art exhibitions, increased self-confidence during mock interviews, and heightened awareness among school community members and the public regarding the potential of SEN students.

Table 1: Findings from Special Education and Mainstream Teachers (N = 20)

Item Penilaian	Dapatan (%)	Keterangan Ringkas
Peningkatan keyakinan murid selepas MPK	95%	Jelas peningkatan komunikasi & ekspresi diri
Keberkesanan mock interview	90%	Membantu murid fahami keperluan kerjaya
Kesesuaian aktiviti dengan kebolehan murid	85%	Aktiviti pelbagai aras, boleh disesuaikan
Keperluan kesinambungan program MPK	100%	Disarankan dijadikan aktiviti tahunan

Table 1 presents the findings of a questionnaire administered to 20 Special Education teachers and mainstream teachers who were directly involved in the implementation of the Special Educational Week Program (SEWP). The analysis shows that the majority of teachers agreed that the program had a positive impact on students with special educational needs (SEN) across various domains of personal development.

A total of 95% of respondents reported a significant increase in student self-confidence following participation in the program. This was reflected through observable behavioral changes, such as students being more willing to communicate, express their opinions, and actively participate in open activities such as mock interviews and entrepreneurship exhibitions.

In addition, 90% of teachers stated that the mock interview sessions were highly effective in helping students understand the basic expectations of the working world. Students were observed to be better prepared in terms of self-expression, dress etiquette, and basic communication skills when interacting with industry representatives.

Furthermore, 85% of the teachers agreed that the activities conducted throughout SEWP were appropriate and adaptable to the students' abilities. Differentiated activities such as gross-finetivity, beading crafts, and sales management allowed students of varying skill levels to participate fully without feeling excluded.

Most significantly, 100% of the teachers stated that the program should be continued and institutionalized as an annual school initiative. They viewed SEWP not only as a platform to enhance student skills, but also as a mechanism to raise school-wide awareness of the capabilities of SEN students and support broader inclusive education goals.

Table 2: Findings from External Agencies and Community Participants (N = 11 agencies)

Nama Agensi	Sumbangan	Kesediaan Terlibat Lagi	Impak Terhadap Murid
PROTON	Mock interview, pameran kerjaya	Ya	Tinggi
GIATMARA	Demonstrasi kemahiran vokasional	Ya	Tinggi
JKM & PDK	Kaunseling, hubungan komuniti	Ya	Sederhana
IKBN, Kedai Motor SYM	Sesi kerjaya dan pengenalan alat	Ya	Tinggi
Komuniti dan NGO setempat	Pameran, fasilitator aktiviti	Ya	Sederhana ke tinggi

Table 2 presents the findings from collaboration with 11 external agencies and local community partners involved in the implementation of the Special Educational Week Program (SEWP). These findings highlight the support and readiness of various stakeholders in advancing the inclusive education agenda and improving the employability of students with special educational needs (SEN).

Among the agencies with the highest reported impact on students were PROTON and GIATMARA. PROTON conducted mock interviews and career exhibitions that provided students with firsthand exposure to real interview environments and employment opportunities in the automotive industry. GIATMARA contributed by conducting vocational skill demonstrations that inspired students to consider technical and skill-based careers.

IKBN and SYM Motorcycles also had a strong positive impact on students. Their activities included career talks and hands-on sessions introducing mechanical tools and technology used in real workplaces. The Department of Social Welfare (JKM) and Community-Based Rehabilitation Centres (PDK), representing community and welfare sectors, provided counseling and social development activities. Their contributions were rated as moderate but crucial, particularly in fostering social support and the psychosocial well-being of students.

Meanwhile, local community groups and NGOs played roles as facilitators and exhibition partners. Although their impact was assessed as moderate to high, their involvement reflects the importance of synergy between schools and the community in executing meaningful inclusive education programs. Most notably, 100% of participating agencies expressed their willingness to be involved again in future SEWP programs. This demonstrates that SEWP not only benefits students, but also strengthens strategic collaboration between schools and external stakeholders.

Visual Reflection and Field Observations

Visual data collection was supported by photographic documentation throughout the program. Each image was selected based on elements of active student participation and the observed impact of activities on their personal development. The following are some of the key findings based on image reflection:

Figure 2: *Gross-finetivity activities strengthened gross motor coordination and peer communication skills.*

Figure 3: *Entrepreneurship Day demonstrated students' ability to manage booths, sell products, and calculate their own earnings.*

Figure 4: *Mock Interview sessions showcased students' professional demeanor when interacting with industry representatives.*

Figure 5: *Food Preparation activities reflected the students' mastery of real vocational skills.*

Figure 6: *Bead Craft Exhibition illustrated students' creativity and focus in executing fine motor work.*

Figure 7: Direct collaboration with GIATMARA and training agencies strengthened external community support.

Figure 8: The Feedback Wall reflected positive community reception and appreciation for the SEWP program.

Reflecting on the observations and findings throughout the SEWP implementation, several significant outcomes emerged that extended beyond numerical data. Most notably, the program became a space of empowerment for students with special educational needs (SEN), where they grew visibly in self-confidence, social engagement, and the ability to carry themselves with professionalism. Their transformation was evident as they took initiative, engaged voluntarily, and participated meaningfully across activities—demonstrating that with the right exposure and trust, SEN students are more than capable of thriving in real-world settings. The second cycle of the program further deepened collaborative ties between the school, external agencies, and the community. Agencies such as GIATMARA, PROTON, and IKBN not only offered practical support but showed genuine interest in sustaining long-term partnerships, including vocational upskilling for students. Equally impactful was the strengthening of inclusive culture within the school. The active participation of mainstream students alongside their SEN peers, paired with overwhelmingly positive feedback from teachers and community members, showed that SEWP had successfully bridged social gaps—making inclusion not just an agenda, but a lived experience. These outcomes affirm that inclusive education, when nurtured through authentic community engagement and well-structured programs, can leave a lasting mark on every stakeholder involved.

DISCUSSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The implementation of the Special Educational Week Program (SEWP) at SMK Khir Johari serves as a meaningful intervention in strengthening inclusive education and enhancing the employability of students with special educational needs (SEN). Through two cycles of action research, the program's impact was holistically assessed based on direct observation, field data, and reflective practice by the implementer. These findings align with the goals of action research as outlined by McNiff (2017), which emphasize continuous improvement of practice through lived experiences.

Significant improvements were observed between the first and second cycles, particularly in areas such as planning, strategic collaboration, and student engagement. While the first cycle revealed constraints in agency involvement and community awareness, the second cycle demonstrated a marked increase in both program impact and public reception. The increase in participating agencies—from six to eleven—indicates that efforts to build trust with the external community have begun to bear fruit. Activities such as mock interviews, entrepreneurship fairs, and art exhibitions provided students with direct opportunities to explore their potential within real-world settings. Findings revealed that students displayed greater confidence and active participation, with some even beginning to express interest in pursuing careers in vocational fields. The effectiveness of the program was further supported by survey results indicating that 95% of teachers observed significant improvements in student confidence and social skills.

These results corroborate the findings of Zainun et al. (2020), who emphasized the importance of experiential learning in developing vocational competencies among SEN students. SEWP also aligns with recommendations by Mastam and Zaharudin (2024), who proposed Work-Based Learning (WBL) as a primary approach to preparing students for the workforce. Furthermore, the SEWP program reflects inclusive elements promoted in international initiatives such as Inclusive Schools Week and Neurodiversity Celebration Week (Inclusive Schools Network, 2024; Wikipedia, 2024). The SEWP initiative also contributed to the development of social capital between the school and the community. A study by Zainun et al. (2021) demonstrated that collaboration between schools and external stakeholders through entrepreneurship projects can enhance student competitiveness and foster greater community understanding of SEN students' potential. This was further supported by SEWP's feedback wall, which featured numerous expressions of appreciation and agency commitments to sustained collaboration.

Based on two years of implementation, several key recommendations are proposed to ensure the continued growth and long-term impact of SEWP. First, the program should be aligned more explicitly with transition education components, including structured work training, employer orientation sessions, and individualized career planning focused on Transition Education. In addition, agency involvement should be expanded to include a wider range of sectors such as agriculture, hospitality, technology, and services, enabling students to explore diverse and relevant interest areas through an expanded network of partnerships. To improve assessment and tracking of student outcomes, it is recommended that specific rubrics and indicators be developed to evaluate student performance in vocational, social, and communication domains throughout the program. Additionally, systematic documentation and ongoing publication of SEWP implementation efforts can serve as references at the district and national levels to inform policy refinement and enhance meaningful school-based programming.

Ultimately, exposing teachers to action research methodologies can empower them to serve as change agents within their schools, actively shaping inclusive practices and creating more equitable educational opportunities for all students.

CONCLUSIONS

As a special education teacher, implementing the Special Educational Week Program (SEWP) was never just about fulfilling an annual school requirement. Instead, it became a transformative journey that deeply shaped my professional identity and purpose as an educator. SEWP allowed me to witness the true potential of my students—not only through academic lenses, but also through human, social, and vocational dimensions. Through this program, I was able to adopt a more contextual, inclusive, and student-centered approach to teaching.

Professionally, the experience sharpened my reflective skills as an educator. This action research compelled me to think systematically—to analyze student needs, plan meaningful interventions, observe their outcomes, and continuously improve the process. McNiff's (2017) model of action research provided a solid foundation for me to function as an active classroom researcher. More importantly, it helped me build the confidence to initiate change in a professional and impactful way. In terms of student development, SEWP became a powerful platform that revealed the real capabilities of students with special needs. These students demonstrated growth not only in self-confidence and communication, but also in independence, agency interaction, and an understanding of real-world job structures. Activities such as mock interviews, entrepreneurship, and skill exhibitions gave them authentic experiences that prepared them for life beyond school. Their ability to express themselves genuinely inspired other members of the school community.

The impact on the broader community was equally meaningful. SEWP successfully bridged the gap between school and society through strategic collaborations with external agencies, industry players, parents, and the public. The presence of agencies such as PROTON, GIATMARA, IKBN, and local NGOs offered a clearer view of the capabilities and potential of students with special needs. Positive feedback received through interviews and the feedback wall reflected growing public awareness and appreciation for special education and the principles of inclusion. In conclusion, SEWP should be seen as more than just a school project. It represents a holistic, structured, and high-impact intervention model for special education. With proper documentation and dissemination as the best practice, SEWP has the potential to be scaled up across other schools. I truly believe that change doesn't always need to start with top-level policies or large systems; it can begin with a single teacher, one idea, and one deliberate action. SEWP stands as proof that when teachers are given the space and trust to lead, they can drive meaningful changes for students, communities, and the education system.

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